

IMPACT BEHAVIOR OF A SIMPLE MULTIFUNCTIONAL PLATE STRUCTURE

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1 Introduction

Impacts of micrometeoroids and space debris on vehicles moving in space are a recognized threat to space missions. The consequences of meteoroid and debris impacts on a spacecraft can vary widely, from small surface indentation to clear hole perforations that can lead to the penetration of the impacting object in a spacecraft. Close to the earth surface, where much man-made debris is present, the probability of impacts with debris is particularly high. Even if the structural integrity is not fully compromised, clear hole penetrations could be extremely damaging if they affect tanks containing gases which are necessary to complete long lasting missions, even more so when human beings are on board. Therefore there is the clear need of self-healing materials capable of immediately closing holes generated by impacts. In general, systems capable to close holes generated by impacts could find large application for anti-leakage purposes, for example in fuel or chemical storage, especially in environments where perforating impacts represent a possible loading condition. The military and aerospace field definitely represent two such environments. In those two fields a self-healing material could be primary applied to fuel storage tanks of airplanes and ground vehicles, where even a small perforation can have catastrophic consequences due to leakage of the fuel.

The ethylene-co-methacrylic acid ionomer has been observed to self-heal after an impact event [[1], [2], [3], [4], [5]]. The self-healing performance depends on the projectile size, target thickness, impact velocity and temperature. The main advantage of the ionomer is that its self-healing response is an inherent behavior of the material [1], it occurs

instantly without external intervention. This self-healing behavior makes them very attractive for fields where impact loading is common.

In this work, the impact behavior of a multifunctional plate structure, consisting of a carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) laminate and ionomer plate joined together, is investigated experimentally and numerically. The two materials are used together in order to obtain a multilayer plate that can self-repair holes generated by an impact event, thanks to the ionomer, and act as a structural part thanks to the CFRP. The choice of a composite material for the structural part of the panel is motivated by its high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios. In applications such as aerospace structures, where weight reduction is an important issue, composite materials represent an attractive choice. Currently, almost every aerospace company is developing products made with fiber-reinforced composite materials [6].

Impact phenomena are very complex and depend on a number of parameters such as the projectile mass and shape, impact velocity, impact angle, target geometry, and properties of the target and impactor materials. Traditionally the impact phenomenon can be classified, based on the impact velocity, into low (up to one hundred meters per second), medium (about few hundred meters per second), high (from few hundred meters to few kilometers per second) and hyper (above few kilometers per second) velocity impacts. In the experiments presented in this paper, the multifunctional panel samples were impacted by aluminum spheres. The impact velocities ranged from 900 m/s to 1200 m/s, which fall in the class of high velocity impacts. The objective of the impact tests of the multifunctional plate structure was to investigate the self-healing

ability of the ionomer in the case of an impact event, when used in combination with the CFRP and as the inner layer, as the projectile first struck the CFRP and then the ionomer. So far only direct exposure of the ionomer to the projectile impact resulted in hole closure [[4], [5]], thus its self-healing ability as an inner layer is quite unknown. Beside testing the multi-functionality (hole closure), experimental tests also provide valuable data for the characterization of the mechanical behavior of the panel in impact scenarios. In this paper experimental and numerical results will be presented and compared.

2 Multifunctional panel

In this study, a ionomer plate has been attached to a woven carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminate in order to form a multilayer plate structure (Fig. 1) that can perform two functions: 1) support loads acting on it and 2) close holes generated by impacts. Such a panel represents a very simple multifunctional plate structure. In this multifunctional structure the ethylene-co-methacrylic acid ionomer is used to provide a self-healing ability, while CFRP is applied to give the structural function to the panel assembly.

Six multifunctional panel samples were manufactured. Three samples have a composite laminate layer 1.1 millimeters thick and three samples have a composite laminate layer 2.2 millimeters thick. In all samples the thickness of the ionomer layer was 2 millimeters. The woven carbon / epoxy composite laminate layer is made up of four and eight laminas in the case of 1.1 and 2.2 millimeters thick laminate, respectively. Each lamina consists of a carbon-fabric/epoxy composite. The fabric has a five harness satin weave of carbon fibers. The stacking sequence of the laminas in a 2.2 mm thick laminate is [0/45/-45/0]₂, while that in the 1.1 mm thick laminate is [0/45/-45/0].

3 Experiments

3.1 Experimental set-up

Impact tests were carried out at the CISAS hypervelocity impact facility (HVI) [7]. A two-stage light gas gun (LGG) was used. In this facility the projectile is pushed by a system of compressed gas through piston action and controlled by dedicated valves [8]. Fig. 2 shows the schematic of the CISAS LGG.

The facility is provided with a vacuum chamber where the target is placed and with a laser barrier system to measure projectile velocity.

CISAS LGG is able to accelerate particles from 0.6 up to 3 mm at speed up to 6 km/s [9] but it has been recently updated to extend shooting capabilities to particles up to 12 mm in diameter.

For the test campaign reported in this paper a special set-up provided with a ballistic pendulum system has been used to locate the target. The experimental configuration can be seen in Fig. 3 [3].

The target was hanged to the system by four springs, a copper witness plate was fixed to the ballistic pendulum and a triangulation laser was used in order to measure the momentum transferred to the witness plate after the impact.

Six tests were conducted using aluminum spherical projectiles. The target panels, as described in section 2, were composed by a layer of CFRP and a layer of ethylene-co-methacrylic acid ionomer Surlyn® 8940 (DuPont) with a density of 0.95 g/cm³. The polymer used was characterized by a content of 5.4 mol% acid groups, of which 30% neutralized with sodium [4].

For this study 3 tests were carried out using a panel composed by a CFRP 2.2 mm thick and a Surlyn® 8940 2.0 mm thick, then 3 tests were conducted using a panel of CFRP 1.1 mm thick and a Surlyn® 8940 2.0 mm thick.

Both impact on CFRP side and Surlyn® 8940 side were investigated.

The test matrix is presented in Tab. 1. The impact velocities studied were about 1.1 ± 0.1 km/s and all impacts were normal to the target (impact angle of 0°). Impact conditions were chosen in order to keep the same target-thickness to projectile-diameter ratio for the two type of targets, taking into account the uncertainty in target thickness measurement and the projectile dimensions availability.

3.2 Results

Preliminary results of experimental tests are reported in Tab. 2 and Tab. 3.

Preliminary results show that complete perforation occurred in the case of larger projectiles both in the case of direct impact onto CFRP and in the case of direct impact onto ionomer surface. For impacts of smaller projectiles perforation was not complete or the hole on ionomer side appeared to be totally healed.

The damage on the target was then analysed through visual inspection and image analysis. Results were investigated by means of superficial damage extension measurements and ionomer re-healing capability study.

3.2.1 Post impact target inspection

The damage extension for CFRP and internal/external hole for ionomer as presented in Fig. 4 were considered. Damage extension for CFRP refers to surface damage maximum visible extension. The external hole for ionomer refers to not damaged/refused area limit for ionomer.

CFRP damage extension and ionomer hole diameter measurement is based on analysis of high resolution scanner image of the target after the impact (Fig. 4). Damage extension is calculated by means of MATLAB procedure for hole almost elliptical fitting of internal (clear hole) and external (maximum surface extension) damaged area. The results are reported in Tab. 3.

A first analysis on perforation as function of target thickness t_t to projectile diameter d_p ratio (Tab. 2) showed that the limit for complete perforation occurred for $0.9 < t_t/d_p < 1.2$, while no perforation limit is for $t_t/d_p \geq 1.3$. $t_t/d_p = 1.2$ seemed to be the limit for ionomer complete rehealing.

Analysing the CFRP maximum surface damage (Fig. 5), it seemed to have the same behavior as function of t_t/d_p in the two impact side cases. It can also be noticed that CFRP damage is larger for impacts on ionomer side. Damage extension decreased for smaller projectiles, but the decreasing seemed to be faster with the decreasing of t_t/d_p ; hence target thickness seemed to have higher weight.

Visual inspection showed for each shot and in all cases a larger extension of damage on CFRP with respect to the damage on the ionomer surface.

Damage on CFRP is larger in horizontal direction, probably correlated to the weave type.

Collecting information about internal wider delamination was not easy. Some superficial cracks departed in the horizontal and vertical direction indicating some surface delamination occurrence.

Damage on ionomer layer presented as a clear hole, in the case of perforating shots, surrounded by an almost circular area of fused material, probably the rehealed area.

3.2.2 Self-healing

Self-healing capability of ionomer layer was analysed by comparing the internal vs. external hole. The ratio of the two diameters as function of t_t/d_p is plotted in Fig. 6. This function decreased in the case of impact onto ionomer side. This fact could be the result of a higher healing ability of the ionomer in the case of a direct impact. The ratio decreased also for smaller projectiles. This could be explained with the fact that decreasing size projectiles pass through the same thickness ionomer layer, even if the t_t/d_p is kept quite constant.

4 Numerical model

4.1 Introduction

Due to the high cost of experimental tests on one side, and improvement of numerical codes capabilities for non-linear dynamics simulations on the other side, there is a tendency to use simulations whenever possible. The main advantage of the numerical codes is the possibility to investigate a large number of impact conditions, like various velocities, geometries of the target and projectile, materials, and so on, which is often not possible or available to perform experimentally.

In this section the numerical model of the impact tests from section 3 is presented. The numerical simulations were performed using ANSYS AUTODYN. The AUTODYN program is a general-purpose engineering software package that uses finite difference, finite volume, and finite element techniques to solve a wide variety of non-linear problems in solid, fluid and gas dynamics [10]. Such numerical codes are also known as ‘‘hydrocodes’’.

4.2 Numerical set-up

In this study, the Lagrange processor in 3D was used to model the target and projectile. As the targets were impacted approximately at their center, only one quarter of the plate was modeled, Fig. 7. In the impact zone cubic cells with a side length of 0.275 mm were used for the target, and similar cell size was used also for the projectile. The cell size of the target gradually increases toward the plate boundary. The projectile was placed 0.1 mm above the target and an initial velocity, that corresponds to the experimental one, was specified for it. As the plate was attached to four springs, one per corner, it was assumed that the target is free to move in the

thickness direction for very small displacements that occur in the perforation time, so no boundary conditions were applied to the target. Indeed, in the simulations it was observed that the plate boundary displacement is on the order of 10^{-4} millimeters or less at the time of complete perforation. No data was available for the CFRP-ionomer interface, so the two plates were not connected, but were placed close to each other. To overcome problems caused by excessive mesh distortion the erosion algorithm was used. Instantaneous geometric strain was used for the erosion model. The material models used for each material (CFRP, ionomer and aluminum) are briefly described in the following.

4.3 Material models

4.3.1 Woven carbon fibre reinforced plastics

The composite material was modeled using the AMMHIS (advanced material model for hypervelocity impact simulation) material model available in ANSYS AUTODYN. This material model calculates in an orthotropic material the contributions to pressure from the isotropic and deviatoric strain components, and the contributions to the deviatoric stress from deviatoric strains [10]. A brief description of the features of the model is given below.

Orthotropic materials have three orthogonal planes of symmetry. Directions normal to the planes of symmetry correspond to the three principal directions of an orthotropic material. The stress-strain relation for a linearly elastic orthotropic material is given as [6]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{31} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{33} \\ \varepsilon_{23} \\ \varepsilon_{31} \\ \varepsilon_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{ij} are the stress components, ε_{ij} are the strain components, and C_{ij} are the stiffness matrix components. Components of the stiffness matrix can be calculated from the elastic material constants, E_i , ν_{ij} and G_{ij} .

In order to include non-linear shock effects in the above linear relations, it is desirable to separate the

volumetric (thermodynamic) response of the material from its ability to carry shear loads (strength) [10]. To this purpose it is necessary to split the total strain into volumetric (ε_v) and deviatoric (ε_{ij}^d) components. The volumetric strain is defined as:

$$\varepsilon_{vol} = \varepsilon_{11} + \varepsilon_{22} + \varepsilon_{33} \quad (2)$$

Using equations (1) and (2), the linear elastic stress-strain relation for an orthotropic material can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{31} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{3}\varepsilon_{vol} + \varepsilon_{11}^d \\ \frac{1}{3}\varepsilon_{vol} + \varepsilon_{22}^d \\ \frac{1}{3}\varepsilon_{vol} + \varepsilon_{33}^d \\ \varepsilon_{23}^d \\ \varepsilon_{31}^d \\ \varepsilon_{12}^d \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Using the definition of the pressure as the average of the direct stresses:

$$P = -\frac{1}{3}(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \quad (4)$$

and substituting the direct stresses from (3) into equation (4) the following expression for the pressure is obtained

$$\begin{aligned} P = & -\frac{1}{9}[C_{11} + C_{22} + C_{33} + 2(C_{12} + C_{23} + C_{31})]\varepsilon_{vol} \\ & -\frac{1}{3}[C_{11} + C_{12} + C_{13}]\varepsilon_{11}^d \\ & -\frac{1}{3}[C_{21} + C_{22} + C_{23}]\varepsilon_{22}^d \\ & -\frac{1}{3}[C_{31} + C_{32} + C_{33}]\varepsilon_{33}^d \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

From equation (5) the contribution to the pressure of volumetric and deviatoric components of strain can be clearly identified. The first term on the right hand side of (5) can be used to define the volumetric (thermodynamic) response of an orthotropic material in which the effective bulk modulus of the material K' is given as [10]:

$$K' = \frac{1}{9} [C_{11} + C_{22} + C_{33} + 2(C_{12} + C_{23} + C_{31})] \quad (6)$$

The first term on the right hand side of (5) represents the linear relationship between the pressure and the volumetric strain. In order to account for the non-linear relationship between pressure and volumetric strain, the first term on the right hand side of (5) is replaced by a non-linear relation between the pressure and volumetric strain. To this end the following polynomial equation of state is used instead of the first term on the right hand side of equation (5):

$$P = K' \varepsilon_{vol} + A_2 (\varepsilon_{vol})^2 + A_3 (\varepsilon_{vol})^3 + (B_0 + B_1 \varepsilon_{vol}) \rho_0 e \quad (7)$$

where A_2 , A_3 , B_0 and B_1 are material constants obtainable from inverse flyer plate tests, ρ_0 is the initial density and e is the specific internal energy.

To model the onset of material failure the ‘‘Material Stress/Strain’’ orthotropic failure initiation model is used. This model allows different tensile and shear failure stresses and strains for each of the principal directions. The limiting values of the stresses and strains are specified by the user. When the specified value is reached failure is initiated in a principal direction. For the post failure response the ‘‘Orthotropic Post-Failure Response’’ is used. This option was developed specifically for simulating the performance and failure, including delamination, of fibre reinforced composite materials [10]. For all failure modes, on failure initiation, the stress in the failed material directions are set to zero and the stresses in the other directions are modified in accordance with the loss of Poisson’s effect. After failure initiation, the failed material stiffness and strength properties are modified depending on the failure initiation modes [10].

The material properties for a woven carbon fibre reinforced plastics used in this study are given in Tab. 4. The data are obtained from different literature sources and some data are assumed. The polynomial equation of state constants were calculated following the procedure given in [[11], [12]]. For this procedure a slope of the $u_p - U_s$ (u_p – particle velocity, U_s – shock velocity) curve is taken as $s=0,92$ [13].

4.3.2 Ionomer

For the ionomer a linear equation of state, given in the following expression, is used:

$$p = K\mu \quad (8)$$

In equation (8) K is the bulk modulus and $\mu = (\rho/\rho_0) - 1$, where ρ is the density and ρ_0 is the initial density. In order to model the strength effects of the ionomer the ‘‘Multilinear Isotropic Hardening’’ plasticity model is used. In this model the data of the plastic strain vs. stress is required. Those data are obtained from [6]. The stress vs. strain curve is approximated by a piecewise-linear function through ten points. A hydrodynamic tensile failure model was also used. A constant hydrodynamic tensile limit of the material should be specified for this failure model. If the value of the hydrodynamic pressure in a cell falls below this limit value bulk failure is assumed to have occurred [10]. This model avoids catastrophic failure, but because of its simplicity it can be only a rough approximation of reality. A value of $-1.0E+06$ kPa was chosen for the hydrodynamic tensile limit.

Only the initial deformation of the ionomer was treated in this study, so that no self-healing behavior was modeled.

The values of the ionomer density, Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio are equal to 0.95 g/cm³, 350 MPa, and 0.4 , respectively.

4.3.3 Aluminum

The projectile is made of Aluminum 1100. For this material a ‘‘Shock’’ equation of state of the following form is used [10]:

$$p = p_H + \Gamma \rho (e - e_H) \quad (9)$$

In equation (9) is assumed that $\Gamma \rho = \Gamma_0 \rho_0 = \text{constant}$ and

$$p_H = \frac{\rho_0 c_0^2 (1 + \mu)}{[1 - (s - 1)\mu]^2} \quad (10)$$

$$e_H = \frac{1}{2} \frac{p_H}{\rho_0} \left(\frac{\mu}{1 + \mu} \right) \quad (11)$$

In (9), (10) and (11) Γ is the Gruneisen Gamma, ρ is the density, e is the specific internal energy, ρ_0 is the initial density, c_0 is the bulk sound speed, μ is the

compression ($\mu = (\rho/\rho_0) - 1$) and s is the slope of the $u_p - U_s$ curve (u_p – particle velocity, U_s – shock velocity). The data for the equation of state is taken from [14].

The strength response of aluminum is modeled using the Johnson-Cook strength model [15]. In this model the yield stress is defined as:

$$Y = \left[A + B \varepsilon_p^n \right] \left[1 + C \log \varepsilon_p^* \right] \left[1 - T_H^m \right] \quad (12)$$

where A , B , C , n and m are material constants, ε_p is the effective plastic strain, ε_p^* is the normalized effective plastic strain rate, and T_H is the homologous temperature [$T_H = (T - T_{room}) / (T_{melt} - T_{room})$]. The Johnson-Cook model is suitable for materials subjected to large strains, high strain rates and high temperatures. Failure was modeled using the Johnson-Cook failure model. The input parameters used for the Johnson-Cook strength and failure model for aluminum 1100 were taken from [16].

5 Results comparison and preliminary model validation

One parameter used for the comparison of experiments and simulations is the hole diameter on the ionomer side.

The experimental data are presented in section 3, while in Tab. 5 the numerical results are reported. In Fig. 8 the numerical and experimental values of the hole diameter for the ionomer are given. The hole obtained numerically is compared with the experimental external hole, because self-healing was not modeled numerically. For the ionomer external hole diameter disagreement between the experimental and numerical values is found for the cases when the impact occurred on the CFRP side. When impact occurs on the ionomer side the numerical and experimental values agree well. The discrepancies in Fig. 8 are probably due to the limitations of the material model used for the ionomer, as the linear equation of state was used because no other material data were available.

In Fig. 9 the extension of visible damage on the surface of the CFRP side of the multifunctional panel sample is plotted. Both experimental and numerical results are plotted. The data for the impact on the CFRP side agree well, while that for the impact on the ionomer side show some difference. The discrepancy for the thinner multifunctional panel (shot no. 8923 – impact on ionomer side)

increases because the fraction of ionomer in the total thickness of the panel increases, and consequently the panel response becomes more influenced by the ionomer.

Fig. 10 shows the numerically obtained damage pattern on the CFRP for the impact no. 8905. The dominant failure mode is delamination and in plane shear failure. By observing the panel sample from shot 8905 detachment of the superficial layer can be seen (Fig. 11), which actually indicates that delamination and in plane shear failure occurred. In order to observe the sample impacted area in more detail, imaging by scanning electron microscope (SEM) was done (Fig. 11).

In the numerical model damage extends predominantly in the two fiber directions, while in the post impact sample damage is visible mainly in the horizontal direction (Fig. 11). The domination of the detachment in the horizontal direction is probably caused by the weave type, as the material detachment is following the direction of the upper threads that are passing over four lower threads.

Fig. 11 shows that there is a delaminated area also in the vertical direction, where close to the hole the material is rising up and longitudinal cracks are observed. With the SEM the extent of delamination cannot be determined. Damage detection techniques have to be used for the examination of the target interior, in order to quantify the total damage and further validate the numerical model.

6 Conclusions

The ionomer self-healing performance in a multilayer plate structure, consisting of woven CFRP and ionomer, was investigated experimentally. It was observed that the ionomer performance is conditioned by its location in the structure. If it is directly exposed to the impact it heals much better, with respect to a case where the impactor first strikes the CFRP and then passes through the ionomer. In the latter case the ionomer self-healing performance seems to be greatly reduced. Numerical simulations of the experimental tests were also performed. A relatively good agreement exists between simulations and experiments for the damage on the surface of the CFRP. More discrepancy is found in the case when the impactor hits the ionomer side first. Also, larger disagreement between numerical and experimental results is found in the external hole confrontation for the ionomer. This indicates that the

material model used for the ionomer should be revisited, and ionomer data for other types of equation of state are needed.

Further damage inspection of the multifunctional panel has to be performed for the complete validation of the simulations. To this end, ultrasonic nondestructive testing will be used to examine the target interior. Also analysis on witness plate damage and ballistic pendulum measurements will be studied and presented in future works.

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TABLES

Shot No.	ID _t	t _{CFRP} (mm)	t _{Ion} (mm)	v _p (km/s)	d _p (mm)	Impact side
8905	D	2.2	2.0	1.20	5.6	cfrp
8906	F	2.2	2.0	1.20	5.6	ionomer
8908	E	2.2	2.0	1.20	3.5	cfrp
8922	A	1.1	2.0	1.00	3.5	cfrp
8923	B	1.1	2.0	1.07	3.5	ionomer
8925	C	1.1	2.0	0.94	2.3	cfrp

Tab. 1. Test cases. ID_t is the target ID, t_{CFRP} is the thickness of CFRP layer; t_{Ion} is the thickness of the Ionomer layer, v_p is the projectile velocity and d_p is the projectile diameter.

Shot No.	Sample	t/d _p	Impact side	P/ NP/ PR
8905	D	0.75	cfrp	P
8906	F	0.75	ionomer	P
8908	E	1.20	cfrp	PR
8922	A	0.89	cfrp	P
8923	B	0.89	ionomer	P
8925	C	1.35	cfrp	NP

Tab. 2. Perforation results. t_t is the target total thickness, d_p is the projectile diameter, P means complete perforation, NP means no perforation, PR means perforation followed by a complete rehealing.

Shot No.	CFRP, d _{damage} (mm)	Ionomer, d _{hole} (mm)	
		d _{int}	d _{ext}
8905	14.8	3.6	7.7
8906	18.7	2.4	6.6
8908	11.2	0	3.9
8922	7.1	1.6	4.2
8923	13.4	1.0	3.1
8925	4.6	0	4.2

Tab. 3. Experimental CFRP damage extension (d_{damage}) and ionomer internal/external hole diameters (d_{int} / d_{ext}) obtained by image analysis. All diameters are in mm and are representative of average values.

Parameter	Value
<u>Equation of state: Orthotropic</u>	
Reference density (g/cm ³)	1.550
Young modulus 11 (kPa)	7.000E+07
Young modulus 22 (kPa)	7.000E+07
Young modulus 33 (kPa)	1.200E+07
Poisson ratio 12	0.0500
Poisson ratio 23	0.0257
Poisson ratio 31	0.0077
Shear modulus 12 (kPa)	3.500E+06
Shear modulus 23 (kPa)	3.000E+06
Shear modulus 31 (kPa)	3.000E+06
<u>Volumetric response: Polynomial</u>	
Bulk modulus A ₁ (kPa)	1.79139E+07
Parameter A ₂ (kPa)	1.65950E+07
Parameter A ₃ (kPa)	-2.5223E+06
Parameter B ₀	0.84
Parameter B ₁	0.84
Parameter T ₁ (kPa)	1.79139E+07
Parameter T ₂ (kPa)	1.65950E+07
<u>Strength: Elastic</u>	
Shear modulus (kPa)	3.500E+06
<u>Failure: Material Stress/Strain</u>	
Tensile failure stress 11 (kPa)	6.000E+05
Tensile failure stress 22 (kPa)	6.000E+05
Tensile failure stress 33 (kPa)	6.000E+04
Maximum shear stress 12 (kPa)	7.000E+04
Maximum shear stress 23 (kPa)	7.500E+04
Maximum shear stress 31 (kPa)	8.000E+04
Tensile failure strain 11	0.008570
Tensile failure strain 22	0.008570
Tensile failure strain 33	0.0050
Maximum shear strain 12	0.0200
Maximum shear strain 23	0.0250
Maximum shear strain 31	0.0250
Failed in 11, failure mode	11 only
Failed in 22, failure mode	22 only
Failed in 33, failure mode	33 only
Failed in 12, failure mode	12 & 33 only
Failed in 23, failure mode	23 & 33 only
Failed in 31, failure mode	31 & 33 only

Tab. 4. Material data for woven carbon / epoxy composite.

Shot No.	CFRP (mm)		Ionomer, d_{hole} (mm)
	$d_{d,1}$	$d_{d,2}$	
8905	26.40	27.12	10.54
8906	16.50	15.96	7.16
8908	14.28	14.82	7.78
8922	8.82	9.92	7.42
8923	7.70	7.68	3.76
8925	4.92	4.92	3.50

Tab. 5. Numerical data for the CFRP damage extension in direction 1 ($d_{d,1}$), damage extension in 2 ($d_{d,2}$) and ionomer hole diameter (d_{hole}).

FIGURES

Fig. 1. A multifunctional panel sample.

Fig. 2. CISAS LGG schematic [8].

Fig. 3. Experiment configuration scheme.

Fig. 4. Example of CFRP damage extension and ionomer internal / external diameter identification. Figure a) shows the case of damage extension (dotted line) for CFRP side. Figure b) shows the case of internal (solid line) and external (dotted line) hole for ionomer side.

Fig. 5. Maximum damage extension on CFRP surface as function of target thickness to projectile diameter ratio. Empty markers refer to shot on CFRP side, while filled markers refer to shot on Ionomer side.

Fig. 6. Re-healing Ionomer capability investigated as ratio between Ionomer internal and external hole as function of target thickness to projectile diameter ratio. Empty markers refer to shot on CFRP side, while filled markers refer to shot on Ionomer side.

Fig. 7. Projectile and target at the initial step, only one quarter of the model is shown.

Fig. 8. Experimental and numerical external hole diameter for the Ionomer as function of target thickness to projectile diameter ratio.

Fig. 9. Experimental and numerical data for the damage extension on CFRP as function of target thickness to projectile diameter ratio.

Fig. 10. Material damage from numerical simulation, shot 8905.

Fig. 11. High resolution scan (left) and SEM (right) image of the damage after impact test 8905.